

TOSHKENT DAVLAT IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI BOSH PROKURATURASI
HUZURIDAGI IQTISODIY JINOYATLARGA QARSHI
KURASHISH DEPARTAMENT

“RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA IQTISODIY
XAVFSIZLIKNI TA’MINLASH: MUAMMOLAR VA YECHIMLAR
MAVZUSIDAGI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI TO‘PLAMI

FUQAROLAR PLASTIK KARTALARI KIBRXAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASH
TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH” (MY CARD MOBIL ILOVASI)

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT

Ilmiy elektron jurnal

Elektron nashr. 319 sahifa.
2026-yil, fevral.

Bosh muharrir:
Mo'minov Baxodir Boltaevich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Nasimov Rashid

Muharrir:
Ulug'ova Baxtiniso Norpulatovna

Musahhih:
Ulug'ova Baxtiniso Norpulatovna

Dizayner:
Egamberdiyev Elyor

Tahrir hay'ati:

- Mo'minov Bahodir (hay'at raisi)
- Rashid Nasimov (hay'at raisi o'rinbosari)
- Marat Raxmatullayev (O'zbekiston)
- Muxammadjon Musaev (O'zbekiston)
- O'tkir Xamdamiyev (O'zbekiston)
- Ali Xikmet (AQSh)
- Dmitriy Rodionov (Rossiya)
- Dilnoza Muhammadieva (O'zbekiston)
- Gayrat Ishanxodjaev (O'zbekiston)
- Nodir Rahimov (O'zbekiston)
- Akmal Abdusalomov (J. Koreya)
- Xamza Eshankulov (O'zbekiston)
- Iles Xujayarov (O'zbekiston)
- Mexriddin Raximov (O'zbekiston)
- Murodjon Sultanov (O'zbekiston)
- Bekmurodov Ulug'bek (O'zbekiston)
- Alisher Qobilov (O'zbekiston)
- Iroda Abdullaeva (O'zbekiston)
- Burova Ekaterina (Rossiya)
- Xodiyeva Gulmira (O'zbekiston)
- Sultonboyeva Munira (O'zbekiston)

Jamoatchilik kengashi:

- Gul Tokdemir (Turkiya)
- Umid Axmedov (Daniya)
- Marko Porta (Italiya)
- Xristo Beloev (Bolgariya)
- Muxriddin Muhitdinov (J.Koreya)
- Boshtyan Brumen (Sloveniya)
- Bibigul Koshoeva (Qirg'iziston)
- Olga Dzyabenco (Ispaniya)
- Stefani Estlund (Lyuksemburg)
- Sanjar Iskandarov (O'zbekiston)
- Aydos Sarsembayev (Qirg'iziston)
- Svetomir Vasilev (Bolgariya)
- Pap Solt (Vengriya)

MUNDARIJA

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA MOLIYA SOHASINING INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	7
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Mamadyarovna Go'zal Norboyevna	
MOLIYAVIY INKLYUZIYA VOSITALARI ORQALI CHEKKA HUDUDLARDA IQTISODIY FAOLLIKNI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	13
Eshov Mansur Po'latovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI BOSH PROKURATURA HUZURIDAGI IQTISODIY JINOYATLARGA QARSHI KURASHISH DEPARTAMENTI FAOLIYATI VA UNING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDAGI O'RNI.....	20
Babadjanov Atxam Axmadjanovich	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫМИ ПРОЦЕССАМИ ДЛЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ.....	26
Ахмедов Самандар Сайфуллоевич	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BOJXONA XIZMATINING FISKAL FAOLIYATIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	32
Farxodov Farrux Furqatovich, Toshpo'lotova E'zoza Latifjonovna	
SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT ULUSHINI QISQARTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	38
Mamatkulov Salimjon Raxmonkulovich	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BOJXONA TO'LOVLARINI UNDIRISHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING AYRIM MASALALARI.....	43
Pardayev To'liqin Nasirovich	
QARZ MUNOSABATLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH: IQTISODIY VA HUQUQIY MUNOSABATLARDAGI AHAMIYATI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	47
Quramboev Jamshid Rashid o'g'li	
EVALUATING THE EFFICIENCY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN USING A MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION MODEL.....	50
Rakhimberdiev Kuvonchbek Bakhtiyorovich	
TASHQI SAVDO OPERATSIYALARIDA DEBITOR QARZDORLIKLARNI BOSHQARISHNING RAQAMLI MODEL VA RISK-MONITORING TIZIMI.....	56
Tashmuxe'dov Dilmurod Mirabzalovich	
WAYS TO REDUCE THE RISK OF DIGITAL ATTACKS IN BANKING AND GOVERNMENT FINANCIAL SYSTEMS.....	62
M.N. Umarova	
MOLIYALASHTIRISH MANBALARINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISH KICHIK BIZNES IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASH OMILI SIFATIDA.....	69
Abduxakimov Eldor Djaloliddinovich	
TADBIRKORLIK VA KICHIK BIZNESDA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY MASALALARI.....	76
Aliyev Yashnarjon Egamberdiyevich	
MAHALLIY GILAM ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKDA TAHDIDLARNI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	81
Arziyeva Sevinch Shomurot qizi	
TASHQI SAVDODA XATARLARNI KAMAYTIRISHDA SAVDONI MOLIYALASHTIRISH VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	85
Babadjanov Shuhrat Atxamovich	
KORXONALAR IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING KONTSEPTUAL VA METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI.....	92
Jamoliddinov Jobirbek Bohodir o'g'li	

KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINING MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASHNING METODOLOGIK JIHATLARI.....	97
Karimov Alibek Valiyevich	
KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH OMILLARI NOMUTANOSIBLIGINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA’SIRINI VAHOLASH VA UNI BARTARAF ETISH MEXANIZMI.....	102
Kaypnazarova Gulshad Xojamuratovna	
КРИТЕРИИ ОЦЕНКИ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В МАЛОМ БИЗНЕСЕ С ПОМОЩЬЮ SWOT-АНАЛИЗА.....	108
Набиев Бехзод Шавкатович	
TADBIRKORLIK VA KICHIK BIZNESNING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASH HAMDA QO’LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING ILMIY-AMALIY JIHATLARI.....	114
Tashmuxeimedova Yayra Atxamovna, Teshayev Sayimbek	
O’ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNESNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH ORQALI AHOLI BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH YO’LLARI.....	120
Toxirova Mushtariybegim Yashnarjon qizi	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATI KORXONALARIDA MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA’MINLASH STRATEGIYASI.....	124
Tursunov Bobir Ortikmirzayevich, Umarova Nargiza Xoldarovna	
РАЗРАБОТКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОЙ СТРАТЕГИИ ФИНАНСОВОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ТЕКСТИЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ.....	134
Турсунов Бобир Ортикмирзаевич	
KIMYO SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA’MINLASHDA MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	141
Tursunxo’jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o’g’li	
MAMLAKAT QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATI KORXONALARI MOLIYAVIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMILLARNING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI.....	147
Umarova Nargiza Xoldarovna	
YENGIL SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI.....	154
Sadriddinova Nigora	
RAQAMLI MOLIYAVIY INKLYUZIYA VOSITALARI ORQALI TUMANLAR O’RTASIDAGI IJTIMOYIY FARQNI KAMAYTIRISH MODELI.....	162
Xakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, Tursunov Bobir Ortikmirzayevich, Adashaliyev Baxtiyorjon Valisher o’g’li	
O’ZBEKISTONDA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT KO’LAMINI QISQARTIRISHDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING O’RNI	170
Jaloliddinov Anvar Jaloliddin o’g’li	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT KO’LAMINI QISQARTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH: O’ZBEKISTON BOJXONA ORGANLARI TAJRIBASI	176
Makkamov Z.X., Soatov S.S.	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR ORQALI XALQARO SAVDODA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNI TA’MINLASH MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI BARTARAF ETISH MEXANIZMLARI	182
Muxtorov Boburmirzo Bahodir o’g’li	
RAQAMLI TO’LOV TIZIMLARI VA ELEKTRON HISOB-KITOBARNING YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT ULUSHINI KAMAYTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI.....	188
Norsafarov Bunyodshoh Muhiddinzoda	
PROSPECTIVE INDICATORS FOR MANAGING THE LEGALIZATION OF THE INFORMAL SECTOR AND INFORMAL EMPLOYMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	192
Qoraboyev Nuriddin Pardaboy o’g’li	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOT KO’LAMINI QISQARTIRISHDA TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN AHOLIGA KO’RSATILAYOTGAN BANK XIZMATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING RAQAMLI YO’NALISHLARI... 196	
To’patillayeva Gulnoza Sirojiddin qizi	
BIG DATA TEXNOLOGIYALARI YORDAMIDA SOLIQ RISKLARINI ANIQLASH VA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	201
Yakubova Nargiza Tursunbayevna, Maxmudov Jasurbek Ulug’bek o’g’li	

SOLIQLAR YOKI BOSHQA MAJBURIY TO'LOVLARNI TO'LASHDAN BO'YIN TOVLASH JINOYATI VA UNING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	208
Axmedov Zafar Bozorboyevich	
DAVLATLARNING IQTISODIY JINOYATCHILIKKA QARSHI KURASHDAGI XALQARO HAMKORLIGI: XALQARO TASHKILOTLAR, FATF STANDARTLARI VA AMALIY MEXANIZMLAR.....	213
Tashmuxeimedova Yayra Atxamovna	
IQTISODIY JINOYATLARNI ANIQLASH VA ULARGA QARSHI KURASHISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYALARINING O'RNI.....	221
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, Tursunov Bobir Ortiqmirzayevich, Tashmuxeimedova Yayra Atxamovna	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA AHOLINING MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	226
Azlarova Mushtariybegim Abror qizi	
RAQAMLI TO'LOV TIZIMLARI XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA DAVLAT INSTITUTSIONAL MEXANIZMLARINING ROLI.....	232
Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna, Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna	
MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIK TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI.....	238
Maxmudova Muxlisa Qodirjon qizi, Sattorova Nasiba G'anijon qizi	
AHOLI MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR TAHLILI.....	244
Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna, Muzaffarova Dilbar Mamalatif qizi	
MAHALLIY OLIMLAR TADQIQOTLARIDA MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIK VA BANK XIZMATLARI MASALALARI.....	251
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Maxmudova Muxlisa Qodirjon qizi	
BANK PLASTIK KARTALARI VA SHAXSIY HISOB RAQAMLARINI NAZORAT QILISH TIZIMINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	258
Azlarova Aziza Axrorovna, Sattorova Nasiba G'anijon qizi	
AUTENTIFIKATSIYA SXEMALARINI TAHLIL QILISH VA ULARNING AFZALLIKLARI HAMDA KAMCHILIKLARI.....	265
Ahmedova Nilufar Shukratovna, Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna	
PLASTIK KARTALAR XAVFSIZLIGIGA TA'SIR KO'RSATUVCHI MAVJUD KIBERXAVFSIZLIK TAHDIDLARI TAHLILI.....	272
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Maxmudova Muxlisa Qodirjon qizi	
ILG'OR XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARDA PLASTIK KARTALAR VA RAQAMLI TO'LOVLAR XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASH TAJRIBALARI: FINTECH PLATFORMALARINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI VA MYCARD MOBIL ILOVASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH BO'YICHA TAVSIYALAR.....	278
Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna, Mashrapova Sabina Turobjonovna	
AHOLI MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISHDA IJTIMOY TARMOQLARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MEZONLARI VA INDIKATORLARI.....	285
Eshpulatova Muazzam Barnoyevna	
AHOLINING MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	292
Eshpulatova Muazzam Barnoyevna	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ОЦЕНКИ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЗРЕЛОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ И ЕЁ ВЛИЯНИЕ НА КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТЬ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	298
Назарова Гулчехра Нурмухамбетовна	
ОЦЕНКА ВЛИЯНИЯ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЗРЕЛОСТИ ЭЛЕКТРОННОЙ КОММЕРЦИИ НА КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТЬ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	305
Назарова Гулчехра Нурмухамбетовна	
MOLIVAVIY INKLIZIYADA KIBERXAVFSIZLIKNING O'RNI VA UNING BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: BANK MOBIL ILOVALARI MISOLIDA.....	313
Saydamatova Muxlisabonu Rasuljon qizi	

WAYS TO REDUCE THE RISK OF DIGITAL ATTACKS IN BANKING AND GOVERNMENT FINANCIAL SYSTEMS

M.N. Umarova

Associate Professor,
Department of Economic and Financial Security

Abstract. This article analyzes the increasing types of digital attacks on banking and public financial systems, their impact on economic stability, and advanced approaches to ensuring the security of the financial system. Artificial intelligence-based monitoring systems, international standards, ways to modernize cybersecurity infrastructure, and reduce risks associated with the human factor are substantiated.

Key words: Digital security, banking system, public finance, cyberattacks, financial stability, AI monitoring, cryptography, economic security, financial market, digital banking, e-government, V2S (business-to-customer), V2V (business-to-business), S2V (customer-to-business) business models, e-commerce, physical freedom, cloud computing, hybrid cloud, corporate cloud, internet, digital added value, digital lock-in, self-service, remote use, large data, blockchain.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bank va davlat moliya tizimlariga raqamli hujumlarning tobora ko‘payib borayotgan turlari, ularning iqtisodiy barqarorlikka ta’siri va moliya tizimi xavfsizligini ta’minlashning ilg‘or yondashuvlari tahlil qilinadi. Sun‘iy intellektga asoslangan monitoring tizimlari, xalqaro standartlar, kiberxavfsizlik infratuzilmasini modernizatsiya qilish va inson omili bilan bog‘liq xavflarni kamaytirish usullari asoslanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Raqamli xavfsizlik, bank tizimi, davlat moliya, kiberhujumlar, moliyaviy barqarorlik, AI monitoringi, kriptografiya, iqtisodiy xavfsizlik, moliya bozori, raqamli bank, elektron hukumat, V2S (biznesdan mijozga), V2V (biznesdan biznesga), S2V (mijozdan biznesga) biznes modellari, elektron tijorat, jismoniy erkinlik, bulutli hisoblash, gibrid bulut, korporativ bulut, internet, raqamli qo‘shimcha qiymat, raqamli blokirovka, o‘z-o‘ziga xizmat ko‘rsatish, masofadan foydalanish, katta ma’lumotlar, blokcheyn.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются растущие виды цифровых атак на банковские и государственные финансовые системы, их влияние на экономическую стабильность и передовые подходы к обеспечению безопасности финансовой системы. Обосновываются системы мониторинга на основе искусственного интеллекта, международные стандарты, способы модернизации инфраструктуры кибербезопасности и снижение рисков, связанных с человеческим фактором.

Ключевые слова: цифровая безопасность, банковская система, государственные финансы, кибератаки, финансовая стабильность, мониторинг ИИ, криптография, экономическая безопасность, финансовый рынок, цифровой банкинг, электронное правительство, бизнес-модели V2S (бизнес-клиент), V2V (бизнес-бизнес), S2V (клиент-бизнес), электронная коммерция, физическая свобода, облачные вычисления, гибридное облако, корпоративное облако, интернет, цифровая добавленная стоимость, цифровая зависимость, самообслуживание, удаленное использование, большие данные, блокчейн.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of digital technologies is leading to fundamental changes not only in the economy, but also in society. By reducing information costs, digital technologies significantly reduce the cost of economic and social transactions for governments, companies, and individuals, foster innovation, and make existing activities and services cheaper, faster, and more accessible. In short, digital technologies allow people to use services that they previously did not have access to.

The acceleration of the digital economy is leading to an increase in the share of online services in banking and public financial systems, as well as an increase in the number of cybercrimes. The financial sector is one of the most targeted areas of cyberattacks in the world. According to the International Monetary Fund and BIS, cyberattacks targeting the financial system have increased by 250% in the past 5 years. Therefore, the

issues of early detection of digital attacks, their elimination and strengthening the stability of the system are of strategic importance for the state and private sectors. In today's globalization and digital economy, the stability of financial systems has become a key component of national security. According to statistics from the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund and other international financial institutions, the number of cyberattacks on banking systems increased by 38% in 2023–2024. In particular, cases of data theft and breach of state budget management information systems have increased sharply. Therefore, improving digital protection strategies is an urgent scientific and practical issue.

The process of digital transformation has fundamentally changed the financial sector. The transition of banking services to online platforms and the digitization of state financial systems, while creating convenience, have also created new types of cyber threats. In particular, attacks such as DDoS, phishing, malware, ransomware, SQL injection, man-in-the-middle pose a significant threat to the security of financial information and transactions. This article provides an in-depth analysis of these processes and presents strategies for mitigating risks.

The rapid shift of consumers to e-commerce, the partial replacement of physical retail by online commerce, and the low level of development of financial institutions and banking infrastructure have contributed to the rapid spread of online financial services.

Table 1. Digital strategies of G20 countries

Country	Strategy	Key seeds
USA	Information highway (1992)	Digital communication system. Information telecommunications network.
	National Broadband Licensing Plan (2010)	Broadband connection available. High-speed Internet.
Japan	e-Japan (2001)	Development of research in the field of information infrastructure and technology.
	i-Japan (2004)	Widespread use of digital technologies in industry and services, diversity in practice.
	i-Japan (2009)	Public administration - aimed at government, hospitals and schools.
EU	i-2010 (2005)	Open and competitive digital economy. Information and communication technologies.
	Digital Agenda Europe Strategy 2020	Development of a single digital market.
Great Britain	Digital Great Britain (2009)	Leadership in the digital economy.
	"Digital Economy Law 2010" (2010)	Digital media policy - copyright, Internet domain names, local radio, and video games.
	«Strategy for the Development of the Digital Economy in the years 2015-2018 » (2015)	Scaling up digital innovators; Enhancing user experience; Digital innovators' tools; Developing infrastructure, platforms, and ecosystems; Ensuring sustainability.
France	Digital France 2020	Development of fixed and mobile broadband
	France (2011)	The popularization of digital applications and services, especially e-government or e-commerce.
Australia	National Strategy for the Digital Economy (2011)	e-health, e-education, smart grids, e-government, digital economy, digital media.
Germany China Internet + (2015) Integration of the Internet and other traditional networks	Industry 4.0 (2013)	Cyber-physical systems Internet of Things Cloud computing.
	Digital strategy 2025 (2016)	Digital independence; Digital infrastructure; Information security.
Russia	National Technology Plan (2014)	Energjinet, Xelsnet, Neuronet, Marinet, Avtonet, Aeronet, Texnet.

Country	Strategy	Key seeds
South Korea	Innovations in Manufacturing 3.0 (2014) Manufacturing Innovations Structure 3.0 (2015)	Information Technology + Development.
India	Digital India (2015)	Creating digital infrastructure; Providing digital services; Digital literacy.
China	Internt (2015)	Information and communication technologies; Integration of the Internet and other traditional networks.

Source: Compiled by the author based on UN reports on the digital economy.

All the documents listed in Table 1 are aimed at the development of the digital economy, since in recent years it has become an important factor in the global economy. These data not only show the rapid growth of e-commerce, but also suggest that in the coming years it will significantly contribute to the development of an economy that may not be included in the new system of economic relations. Below is a list of the largest companies in the world by market capitalization:

Table 2. Top 10 largest companies in the world by market capitalization

The name of the company	The market's place in the world is determined by the market.	Market capitalization, billion, dollars
Microsoft	1	1000
Arrle	2	946,2
Amazon	3	948,5
Alrhabet (Google)	4	830,7
Facebook	6	552,0
Berkshire Hathawau	5	532,6
Alibaba Grour	7	481,0
Tencent Holdings limited	8	461,5
JR Morgan Chase	9	376,8
Johnson & Johnson	10	375,9

Source: Yahoo Finance latest online data.

As can be seen from the table above, only 3 of the 10 largest companies in the world (Berkshire Hathaway, J.R. Morgan Chase, Johnson & Johnson) are not engaged in digital business, while all other companies are leading organizations in integral sectors of the digital economy, such as online commerce, social networking, software, and Internet search services. These statistics also clearly demonstrate the need to focus on the digital economy as a modern way to achieve economic prosperity.

Due to the increasing competitive environment in countries, the number of Internet service perators and providers is constantly increasing.

Figure 1. Analysis of economic indicators of the ICT sector in 2024 (www.mitc.uz)

In Uzbekistan, in 2024, general services provided in the ICT sector amounted to 10.6 trillion soms, and exports of communication and information services amounted to 176.0 million dollars. While employment in the information and communications sector is projected to double in 2024 compared to 2022, the volume of computer and programming services is projected to nearly triple (Figure 1).

Today, the banking industry is in a global digital arms race. This year, global banks are investing \$9.7 billion in digital banking capabilities. The US has planned to invest in the amount of US dollars. In many commercial banks, the creation and development of online and mobile banking applications is considered more important than the expansion of traditional bank branches and ATMs.

Banks around the world are already aware of how digital technologies can be used to attract and satisfy customers. The different positions of countries in the global economy, as well as the competitiveness of national economies and enterprises in global markets, can seriously affect the internal and external state of the government, as well as financial security. Therefore, even though the world community seems to be implementing the principles of free trade, almost all countries in the world continue to actively support protectionist measures. As we know, an open economy is an economy that has entered into external economic relations and is developing based on their advantages. The openness of the national economy is one of the main principles of modern market development.

Cyberattacks targeting the financial system are multifaceted, often aiming to steal data, disable the system, disrupt transactions, or cause financial damage. Asosiy hujum turlari:

- DDoS – server overload.
- Phishing – deceiving the user to obtain their data.
- Ransomware – encrypting the system and demanding money.
- MITM – interference in the data transfer process.
- SQL Injection – illegal access to the database.
- Zero-Day – use of undetected vulnerabilities.

These attacks target the most vulnerable parts of the financial system: internet banking, payment systems, state registries, budget payment platforms, central bank networks, etc. Economic losses resulting from cyberattacks are divided into two groups:

Direct losses:

- Theft of client funds.
- Costs of restoring the system and reloading data.
- Costs of updating servers and strengthening cybersecurity.

Indirect losses:

- Loss of customer trust.
- Reduction of the bank's market share.
- Temporary halt to bureaucratic processes in the state system.
- Destabilization of national payment systems.

According to global estimates, a single major cyberattack on the financial system causes an average of \$5–40 million in damage.

Digital risks can be divided into two main categories:

- 1) Internal risks - ignorance or intentional harm from employees.
- 2) External risks - hacking attacks, malware, attacks based on artificial intelligence.

The financial security model can be estimated using the following formula:

$$H_x = (T_h * E_t) / R_h$$

where:

H_x – overall risk level,

T_h – number of detected threats,

E_t – threat effectiveness (assessment coefficient),

R_h – available protection level.

If H_x > 1, it is indicated that the system is at risk.

The following table shows the types of digital attacks and their impact on financial security:(Table 3-4.)

Table 3. Main cyberattacks on banking and public financial systems

No	Type of attack	Description	Risk level	Common objects
1	DDoS	Server overload	High	Banking services, payment systems
2	Phishing	Stealing user information through a fake page	Medium–high	Customers, state portal users
3	Malware / Ransomware	System blocking by malware	Very high	Cash registers, electronic registers
4	MITM	Data retention	Medium	Onlayn to'lovlar
5	SQL injection	Database access	High	Bank databases
6	Zero-day exploit	New undetected vulnerabilities	Very high	Basic infrastructure

Table 4. Impact of cyberattacks on economic indicators in the banking system

Type of consequence	Ta'sir ko'lami	Impact on continuous operation	Economic damage
System failure	2–48 hours	High	5–12% decrease in income
Data theft	Medium–large	Medium	100 thousand – 5 million USD
Reputatsion zarar	Wide	High	8–20% decrease in customer flow
Payment system outage	Big	Very high	Damage to the national economy

Source: Compiled by the author.

Technical protection measures will be aimed at detecting and blocking cyberattacks in real time.

Implementation of Zero Trust Architecture.

Not allowing access to the system until each user and device has been fully identified.

Multi-factor authentication (MFA)

Authentication via SMS token, biometric verification, push notification for bank customers and users of the state system.

Data encryption.

256-bit AES encryption algorithms, modernization of SSL/TLS certificates.

Monitoring based on artificial intelligence.

- Real-time analysis of transactions
- Automatic blocking of suspicious transactions
- Anomaly detection based on typical customer behavior (UEBA)

IDS/IPS systems.

Stopping large-scale attacks before they reach the server.

Based on the above information, when working in the banking sector, it is necessary to take care not only of the protection of corporate and other operational information, but also of the network settings and parameters of network activity on the computer. The issue of data protection in a bank is taken much more seriously than in other organizations. Solving this issue involves organizational, systematic measures that ensure protection.

Thus, it can be said that an important factor stimulating the development of the financial technology market is the development of the Internet and digitalization. If in the early stages of development the financial

technology market was limited to payments and accepting electronic money, today a number of other services are expanding. The prospects for digitizing the financial sector are very high. We can say for sure that in the near future, new products and tools will appear aimed at simplifying financial relations to the maximum.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

There are a number of problems in the development of the digital economy in our country, without solving which the competitiveness of the national economy cannot be ensured, especially in the process of globalization based on ICT. For this reason, based on the results of scientific research, the following recommendations have been formulated to reduce the risk of increasing digital attacks on banking and state financial systems.

1. Improve staff skills.

70% of employees in the financial system do not have sufficient knowledge of cybersecurity - which opens the way to phishing attacks.

2. Strengthen national cybersecurity centers.

Expand the capabilities of CERT, SOC centers and cyber threat monitoring laboratories.

3. Implementation of international standards.

- ISO/IEC 27001
- GDPR (data protection)
- NIST Cybersecurity Framework

4. Cooperation between the public and private sectors.

Creation of platforms for real-time information exchange about threats.

5. For banks:

- Expand biometric authentication systems.
- Manage fraud-detecting AI modules on a single platform.
- Conduct quarterly pentests.

For the public sector:

- Create a "Cyber Shield" - a national cyber defense system.
- Gradually introduce quantum cryptography technologies in public services.
- Establish a single backup center (Backup Data Center).

The level of sophistication of cyberattacks is increasing year by year and poses a direct threat to the stability of banking and state financial systems. The comprehensive implementation of technical, organizational and legal measures significantly reduces the risk of digital attacks. In particular, the use of artificial intelligence, the Zero Trust model, international standards and regular training ensure the stable functioning of the financial system.

It is considered important that an important condition for the development of digital technologies is, first of all, ensuring security in the digital space, forming and developing a regulatory and legal framework that protects the rights of consumers, and introducing mechanisms to combat crime in this area.

List of used literature.

1. Resolution of the Board of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 2/4 dated January 25, 2020. Z.R. Fauziyev. "Computerization of workplaces" - educational manual Tashkent-"Uzbekistan". 2010. 70-94 p.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. RF-5992 dated May 12, 2020 "On the Strategy for Reforming the Banking System of the Republic of Uzbekistan" // National Database of Legal Documents, 13.05.2020 No. 06/20/5992/0581.
3. Yeriashvili N.D., Krivorotov V.V., Kalina A.V. Economic security of the state and regions: a textbook. Unity-Dana, 2015. – 4. Ataniyazov Z. X. "International financial security" teaching methodology 2021 edition.
4. Khodiev B. (2017), Uzbekistan: development of the "digital economy". World economy. Russian foreign economic bulletin. No. 12. p. 3-12.
5. Websites
6. www.gov.uz – Government Portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
7. www.lex.uz – National Database of Legislative Documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
8. www.mf.uz – Official website of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.cbu.uz – Official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan. www.stat.uz – Official website of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

3-SHO‘BA

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT

Ilmiy elektron jurnal

(MAXSUS SON)

Bosh muharriri: Mo'minov Baxodir Boltaevich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari: Nasimov Rashid

Muharrir: Ulug'ova Baxtiniso Norpulatovna

Musahhih: Ulug'ova Baxtiniso Norpulatovna

Dizayner: Egamberdiev Elyor

“Raqamli transformatsiya va sun'iy intellekt” jurnali 23.10.2020-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№1124 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

